

eDNAAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Report containing an inventory of the ongoing and completed eDNA initiatives and repositories, identifying their geographical, ecological and taxonomic coverages

Deliverable 2.2

Work Package 2

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Executive Summary

This report contains an inventory of the ongoing and completed environmental DNA (eDNA) initiatives and repositories, identifying their geographical, ecological and taxonomic coverages. It includes a brief description of the methodologies used to perform the inventorying.

The inventory was sought in three different ways:

- Manual review of 29 resources (eDNA and reference libraries) by the bioinformatics team for 40 properties.
- A questionnaire sent out to eDNA research teams, for which(60) responses were neatly collated.
- Automated(LLM) mining of scientific papers

This inventory allowed us to obtain a good overview of the current initiatives and databases being used for eDNA data sharing and publication and to identify the main gaps and areas for improvement.

Specific gaps

The input and this work was performed by many people of different academic backgrounds bringing their expertise to bear. Findings of this report are input to other tasks notably T3.2 and their iterative feedback improved this report. Please see Table 1 for the main identified gaps.

Table 1: The major gaps identified during the inventory and investigation of eDNA databases

Gap	Description	Comment
eDNA raw sequence data is scattered through many repositories	Much eDNA raw sequence data is external to INSDC archives, which makes it difficult to find or reuse data. We were not able to determine exactly how much, but reviews have estimated up to 50% and this is supported by our LLM investigation.	Smaller archives are often harder to sustain and data can be lost over time.
eDNA sequence storage DBs reference only found in 50-77% of scientific papers	Related to the previous gap, in the LLM investigation at best 77% of scientific papers contain the eDNA sequence storage location.	Caveat, the LLM could probably be tuned more to increase the find rate e.g. with a bigger training set, but there will still be a large gap
Each repository has its own API and little consistency of each API	eDNA raw sequence accession ids are hard to query for or to retrieve from many portals or even their APIs, making federated queries challenging	
Missing important general sample or sequence related metadata	One third of repositories in the survey are missing any general sample or sequence related metadata e.g. GPS coordinate or library_strategy	
Many repositories have no stated processed metadata standards	41/61 repositories of the survey had no stated processed metadata standards.	
Some repositories are using global metadata standards, but many are not	DwC(e.g. OBIS and GBIF) and GSC MixS(e.g. INSDC) are the most common where there are global standards. Indeed there is a MixS TDWG DwC mapping task force. Where eDNA data is buried in papers or in Dryad etc., it is less likely to be using global standards.	GBIF and OBIS on paper are standouts. INSDC possibly hampered by allowing reduced minimal metadata to encourage users to submit.
Difficult to query for aquatic environmental samples/raw sequence records from the INSDC archives	There are multiple parameters needed to get aquatic environmental samples from the INSDC archives in terms of coverage and accuracy.	The metadata is either not present or standardised enough.

Inconsistency of data formats besides fasta(albeit variable) and fastq	Inconsistent formats are one aspect that reduces interoperability and reusability.	
Barcode gene identification is inconsistent in INSDC	In the INSDC, barcode gene nomenclature for eDNA aquatic samples are rarely captured in the "target_gene" field and we determined that only 20% recorded in the study description or title.	The INSDC have no mandated Barcode marker identifiers (Note:. This is not the barcode tag from multiplex sequencing)
INSDC users sometimes using generic and not aquatic specific checklists	Generic sample checklists with less mandatory information are available at INSDC databases. Users sometimes tend to use these checklists instead of the more specific and metadata rich checklists, which limits data searchability and reusability.	
Sampling and archives have been disproportionately lacking from Eastern Europe.	In terms of ecological environments across Europe, there is much diversity of aquatic environments in Europe, in terms of marine, freshwater, ground and brackish. There are eDNA samples in the major seas surrounding Europe and in many countries.	
The INSDC raw sequence only gets the taxonomy id initially provided on submission.	The INSDC only gets the taxID when sequences have been uploaded, it is not up to date when new taxonomies arise or what gets determined by taxonomic identification.	
Generally difficult to specifically find eDNA records.	It is hard in most resources to even get a count of eDNA records. It is sometimes not clear what is a raw eDNA sequence record, what is processed and how to query for such.	The count difficulties of inventorying of eDNA resources illustrated this.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
ASV	Amplicon Sequence Variant
BIOPOLIS	Associação Biopolis
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DDBJ	DNA Data Bank of Japan
EC	European Commission
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EU	European Union
EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Institut Voor Landbouw - En Visserijonderzoek
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IAB	International Advisory Board
IHU	Diethens Panepistimio Ellados
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
LifeWatch-ERIC	E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
NIVA	Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
SU	Sorbonne Université
SYKE	Suomen ympäristökeskus / Finnish Environment Institute
UDE	Universitaet Duisburg-Essen
ULOD	Uniwersytet Lodzki
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
UVEG	Universitat de Valencia
VLIZ	Vlaams Institut Voor de Zee
WP	Work Package(s)
WU	Wageningen University

1. Introduction

Recent years have seen an exponential increase in environmental DNA (eDNA) data generated by numerous laboratories across Europe. This is making use of the power of modern DNA sequencing technologies and bioinformatics to identify organisms in the environment. The enormous volume of eDNA data produced within projects and surveys focusing either on marine, freshwater or transitional waters, is currently scattered among dozens of public databases.

eDNA data includes different data types and associated metadata, such as sample metadata, raw DNA sequence data and related experiment metadata and processed sequences (e.g. Amplicon Sequence Variants, ASVs) (see Table 2 for details). Barcoding data, though not an output of eDNA analysis is relevant as it is used as reference in eDNA studies.

Table 2: Some broad eDNA related data types and metadata.

Object level	Details	Examples of where that data is archived and served from
sample metadata	Metadata about about the geography and environment of the sample, and how it was analysed	Biosamples (e.g. linked to INSDC), GBIF
raw read	Raw DNA sequence (demultiplexed and without removal of primers/adapters) and some experiment metadata. Very limited taxonomy information known, via the sample metadata.	INSDC repositories
processed sequence	The DNA sequence after processing the raw sequencing reads bioinformatically (e.g. through OTU clustering or ASV denoising). Taxonomic identification is made using the reference barcodes	OBIS, GBIF
Reference barcodes	Reference DNA sequence of marker genes for many taxonomic ranks including species.	BOLD, INSDC

Nucleic acid sequence data (DNA and RNA) and the accompanying metadata (annotation about this data) have been captured for over 40 years in the public International Nucleotide

Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) databases: NCBI [Benson 2013], ENA [Yuan 2023] and DDJB [Tanizawa 2023]. Originally much of the contextual metadata being collected was sparse and non-standard and there have been many efforts both within the INSDC and beyond e.g. The Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC) [Field 2011] to improve the quality and coverage. Environmental related metadata is one of those that have particularly benefited from the MIxS standards (checklists and terms) from the GSC and also the Darwin Core Standards(DwC) [Wieczorek 2012]. The development and adoption of DwC by The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)[GBIF 2024] and more recently Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS)[OBIS 2024], has been beneficial to the biodiversity community by increasing standardisation particularly in the observation aspect. Over the decades many including recently [Leigh 2024] have more widely reviewed genetics and genomics archives. In the environmental space the broader environmental scoped GSC and more biodiversity focused DwC to collaborate. Despite all the initiatives and work, there are still large gaps in how eDNA is being handled, stored, archived and shared, hence the need for the eDNAqua-Plan as a whole and the Task 2.2 for eDNA, that is being reported in this document and especially the Tasks 2.3 and 3.2, that will be separately reported.

In this deliverable, we focus mainly on the publication, accessibility and reusability of raw sequence eDNA metadata and data. Other deliverables from this work package are focused on the barcoding reference libraries (D2.1) and the workflows for DNA based monitoring (D2.3).

Much raw sequence has been deposited into storage archives (e.g. INSDC) as repositories. Biodiversity focused portals (e.g. GBIF and OBIS) have mainly observational data albeit some have a limited amount of eDNA raw sequence data too (e.g. OBIS); typically any sequence they have is derived from the analysis of raw sequence data. Some specific resources use and process eDNA sequence data deposited in other archives (e.g. EukBank). Generalised repositories of scientific data (e.g. DRYAD, Zenodo) also contain eDNA raw sequence data. Moreover, there is an undefined volume of unreleased data that is not publicly available and stored on institutional servers. This information remains unlinked with biogeographical, ecosystem, and methodological tags that drastically limits its usage.

There is much scope overlap between resources in the eDNA space and related resources, both world and Europe wide. Fortunately the eDNA archives themselves are some of the least complex parts of this, although as outlined earlier the eDNA if captured at all, could be archived in multiple different resources. Let us first consider some of the most well known and used eDNA related resources used by the aquatic community to show how they relate. The figure below demonstrates that many eDNA related resources submit and or use the sequences in the INSDC (ENA, NCBI, DDJB). It also shows the sheer complexity of the data ecosystem in that most resources do several functions, and in turn some of their output/curations are input for other resources for example: 1) a key input of Protist Ribosomal Reference Database (PR2) is mining of INSDC archives for relevant full-length 18S sequences of protists(mainly not eDNA), after much analysis one of the outputs is a reference library 2) OBIS takes biological oceanic data from a range of sources, including sometimes directly from users and in turn the biodiversity observational data are consumed by GBIF.

Figure 1: A schematic showing where the eDNA repositories fit with some of the broader biodiversity resources in our “automated” inventory. PR2, BOLD, MGNify are part of the broader data landscape.

This report contains an inventory of eDNA repositories and initiatives (focused projects e.g. a “study” on one taxonomic grouping or environment), identifying their geographical, ecological

and taxonomic coverages. It includes a brief description of the methodologies used to perform the inventorying. A brief gap analysis is also carried out.

2. Methods

For performing the inventory of the eDNA repositories and initiatives, a first step was needed to agree on which properties were the most important to document and analyse. These are described in the A section below. The inventorying and subsequent gap analysis on eDNA initiatives and repositories was performed using three different methods (figure 2), to try to widely explore the ecosystem for these properties:

1. Manual review of well known eDNA and reference libraries for the 40 properties.
2. Questionnaire sent out to eDNA research teams.
3. Automated (LLM) mining of scientific papers. This was seen as a complementary method to the manual review and questionnaire survey.

The results for each method were collated into structured forms and then computationally analysed.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the how we explored the problem space in T2.2

A. Determining the Required Metadata Properties

The determination of the required metadata properties for the inventory was a collective effort between WP2 and WP3. Together the teams reviewed and collated the requirements on barcode reference libraries and eDNA repositories in a spreadsheet of metadata properties. Additions, improvements and prioritisation were performed. The 40 properties selected for analysis grouped by main category are listed in Table 3. The description of these properties is available in [Milestone 2.1](#).

Table 3: These are the properties(pre-agreed search criteria) grouped by categories:

Main Category	Sub-categories
---------------	----------------

metadata	data_metadata_link metadata_record_URL DB_standard_consistent DB_mandatory_metadata metadata_file_schema
data_access	record_URL web_interface API application
publication	paper_DOI_number paper_link data_paper_location
db_profile	DB_name DB_use_index DB_using_community env_data_contains annually_updated DB_active DB_curation
db_size	number of records number of records (scaled)
sample_details	GPS_coordinates_available sample_collection
data_format	data_export_format data_file_format
metadata_format	metadata_export_format metadata_file_format
barcode	barcode_taxonomy_confidence barcode_name barcode_certain
sequence_related	sequences_processed
experiment_metadata	DNA_extraction sequence_methodology sequencing_strategy analysis_workflow
primariness	directly_uploaded Primary/Secondary
taxonomic	taxonomy_origin taxonomy_URL taxonomically_identified taxonomical_name

B. Automated metadata inventory of eDNA Public Repositories

A list of eDNA and reference barcode public repositories was compiled using the broad knowledge of the team. The table 3 of metadata properties, with a few pragmatic changes was used as input. The initial investigation of the 29 reference library repositories was distributed amongst ULODZ and IHU bioinformaticians. The teams carefully went through each resource portal reading underlying documentation and downloading some data from the APIs etc., to describe the resources. In some cases it was necessary to contact the resource directly to clarify some questions. The spreadsheets with metadata properties as rows and the repositories as columns were created and completed with the information collected.

The spreadsheets were combined and the nomenclature lightly harmonised, to generate a single combined spreadsheet (version 1.0), the “Joint” tab in the “Databases” spreadsheet.

The seven eDNA related resources were extracted from the above and copied to a new tab and the information further harmonised. More importantly, we investigated gaps and inconsistencies in more detail and incorporated feedback from the wider eDNAquaPlan team. This detailed manual analysis of the eDNA repositories allowed us to gain a deeper understanding of the different resources.

We assessed the number of eDNA raw sequence records in each repository, to get the record count. It is surprisingly difficult to get absolute numbers out of some databases as will be discussed further in this report. For the INSDC databases (ENA, NCBI and DDBJ) they share almost the entirety of their sequence data, so the “aquatic” environment record count should be identical, however as it is difficult in any of them to identify aquatic environmental DNA records as the counts vary widely. By “NCBI” we are referring to both GenBank and the Short Read Archive(SRA).

The eDNA data on OBIS can be accessed through the mapper (<https://mapper.obis.org/?hasextensions=DNADerivedData#>). The generated data layer then gives the links to the original datasets, or allows you to download the whole data layer. eDNA data can also be accessed through the R package robis. Instructions for using the robis package are in the OBIS manual [how-to-find-genetic-data-in-obis](#) and in the vignette [notebook-dnaderiveddata/](#). Both the mapper and the R package are based on the [OBIS API](#), which can also be used to find and download data. When using the API directly, you can filter the Occurrence records by specifying the extension DNADerivedData. The response yields again "total": 19,539,744 records. You can further search through this by scientific name, date, depth, coordinates, country.

We note that all GBIF and the majority of OBIS DNA records are **not** raw sequence eDNA, but analysed DNA sequences.

The collected metadata was then analysed using a python script: [mine bioinformatics eval.py](#). The inventory XLSX file was imported into a [pandas dataframe](#)

and the data was explored using some basic pandas functions. There was little meaningful forthcoming from the analysis. We then decided to explore the relevant data in INSDC as this is where much of the world's eDNA raw sequence is stored.

C. Investigation of INSDC eDNA Records

INSDC shares the fundamental nucleotide public data therefore, with a few exceptions, NCBI, ENA and DDBJ hold the same data. All the INSDC members share minimal metadata standards, available in the [INSDC controlled vocabularies](#). For efficiency we thus only used the INSDC eDNA records using the [ENA API](#). The code used is publicly accessible in GitHub: <https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/wp2/>

Getting the Environmental Raw Sequences Records from ENA

To filter “environmental records” for all the raw sequences, we essentially looked for data associated with samples registered with environmental sample checklists from either NCBI/ DDBJ (e.g. [NCBI metagenome or environmental package](#)) or ENA (e.g. [ENA MixS checklists](#)) and not Human associated. Additionally we included data associated with generic checklists (e.g. [ENA default checklist](#)). Although these may include a large number of non-environmental records, users often use it, because this allows them to submit with the least amount of metadata. The query uses the ENA SWAGGER API and the record data formats are transformed into a Python Pandas dataframe. The resulting data was then filtered using geography, taxonomic, or biome metadata to select the more likely to be aquatic records.

The main ENA API query is coded in [ena_api_calls.py](#) with the wrapping and processing done in [get_environmental_info.py](#). It is schematically shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of querying INSDC for the read_run sequence records

Mining ENA/INSDC to get aquatic readruns

Filtering for Aquatic eDNA in ENA

Geographic information, ecological coverage and taxonomy were used for filtering. For this, we used tags, controlled textual annotations provided to objects, that are available on ENA objects to facilitate search and filtering. These tags label records for example according to its geographic locations and/or taxonomy. Below are the relevant tags used in the queries. More details are available at [ENA documentation](#).

Relevant Tags and rules:

- The tax_tag's for tax_marine, tax_brackish, tax_terrestrial and tax_freshwater are derived from the WoRMS environment assignments.
- The geo_tag's for geo_marine, geo_brackish, geo_terrestrial and geo_freshwater are calculated if the longitude and latitude of the collection coordinates are within certain polygons in shapefiles.
- Aquatic is called where at least one of the tags is from an aquatic environment and the majority of tags are aquatic.

Additional filtering restricted the data frame rows to eDNA possible library_strategies, this obviously included filtering for: 'AMPLICON'. We also allowed: 'WGS', 'RNA-Seq', 'WGA', 'Targeted-Capture' and 'ssRNA-seq'.

By applying these filters we realised that it is complex to mine exclusively aquatic eDNA samples from INSDC repositories like ENA. This difficulty arises from the fact that the metadata is often not available or standardised enough.

Geographic information

For INSDC the most useful geographic information for marine environments is to use the latitude and longitude positions in the sample records. These had been mapped by

computational geometry specific polygons in “shape files” and annotated as tags in the objects at ENA. Therefore we simply queried for the env_marine, freshwater and coastal tags available. These tags are however less reliable for freshwater besides large lakes and wide rivers, as the ponds, rivers and streams are contained in relatively small polygons.

We created lists of European countries and seas(surrounding Europe). We investigated the geo_loc(formerly known as country) values, as these contain the country, ocean or sea. Together these allowed us to investigate various aspects of the data in a European aquatic context. See the [geography.py](#) code for details.

Ecological Coverage

INSDC records recommend the use of [ENVO ontology](#) in the broad and local environmental context metadata. However only about 6% of samples have the broad or local environmental context metadata available. We can however use the geographic and taxonomic properties to inform on the ecological categories.

Taxonomic Coverage

It is mandatory to provide taxonomic information when submitting data to INSDC, thus there is high coverage. In the query we used the tax_marine|freshwater|brackish tags created from the WoRMS taxonomic->environment mappings. We also made use of the NCBI taxonomy hierarchy and examined the taxonomic coverage of organisms in the aquatic eDNA records.

D. Questionnaire based survey

A set of questions were determined and is reported in D2.1. Questionnaires were then sent out to researchers and institutions known to be associated with eDNA research. The information from the filled out questionnaires was collated and aggregated. 64 individuals/organisations were contacted, 53 provided with at least one response and 11 did not respond. The following spreadsheet is where the data was collated: “DNA_survey-Data.xlsx”.

1. Survey Questionnaire Analysis

The analysis of the questionnaire results was performed using a python script [mine_questionnaire_eval.py](#) from the same GitHub repository. The aggregated survey data XLSX file was imported into a [pandas dataframe](#). Because the survey data had been well harmonised, analysis was straightforward. We were able to use many basic pandas functions. [Plotly Express](#) was used for most figures, with [Plotly Graph objects](#) for Sankey plots.

Survey Questionnaire Analysis Methodology Example for Markers

An example analysis method is outlined here for “Markers_Simplified”. We used pandas functions to get frequency lists of all the harmonised marker values. Pandas methods and the Counter function were used to generate a frequency table in both markdown and tsv formats. It was also used as input to generate a pie chart in Plotly Express. For an example please

see [analyse_environmental_info.py](#) (search for: **Markers_Simplified**) and the utilities called from there in [eDNA_utilities.py](#) for details.

Survey Questionnaire Analysis Methodology Example for the Environment

For the questionnaire survey data, this was similarly analysed using panda data frames and both the “Environment” and “Substrate.Env” columns. The same python methods were used, just providing the different column labels as attributes. This good practice thus sped up the analysis and kept the tables and plots consistent.

E. LLM for analysing trends in eDNA Scientific Literature

In this section, we describe how we analysed the content of many scientific publications to extract information to answer questions such as: what is the DNA extraction protocol with the source in protocols.io, what is the strategy used in the experiment, what is the sequencing analysis workflow, where the data is stored, what barcode was used in the experiment, what reference sequence database was used for taxonomic identification. The manual processing team built a training set available at [x Paper content training set - pilot.xlsx](#). The preparation of the dataset consisted of finding publications from the field of biology and answering a series of questions based on the analysed publication. The dataset was then used to re-train the Llama2 language model from Meta Inc[Touvron et al. 2021].

A system consisting of web crawlers was produced to automatically download the content of publications from PubMed and PubMed Central. Subsequently the content of the materials and methods section of the analysed publication was sent to the Llama2 language model, which answered the same questions as the experts from the manual processing team. The first question was whether a given publication describes an experiment performed using eDNA. If the publication was not classified as eDNA, further analyses were rejected. The language model generated false positives when samples collected from the environment were then cultured using cell lines, hence additional verification was applied by asking the model whether this was the case. The data obtained from all these processes were saved into a MongoDB database.

The process of data mining of publications was also carried out using the Llama2 model. The series of answers to each question was placed back into the language model and it was asked to summarise the information provided and calculate statistics. Further analysis of the results was done manually.

The full database of information gathered from scientific papers is available at <not yet known>. The Python code is posted at <https://github.com/orgs/eDNAqua-Plan-project/repositories>.

2. Results and High Level Analysis

A. Metadata inventory of eDNA Public Repositories

The seven eDNA repositories that were selected to be analysed are summarised (table 4).

Table 4: A summary of the characterisation of the seven eDNA repositories analysed

Database Name	Is eDNA public repository?	URL	Description (free text)	Specificity [taxon specific (value: low) or generalised (value: high) database]	Accessibility	Notes
Mitofish	False(mainly a biodiversity portal)	http://mitofish.aori.u-tokyo.ac.jp	Mitofish is a database of fish mitochondrial genomes (mitogenomes) that includes powerful and precise <i>de novo</i> annotations for mitogenome sequences.	Low (fish)	http://mitofish.aori.u-tokyo.ac.jp	Reports 843,537 sequences (all are directly fish mitochondria).
NCBI	True	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/	Perhaps the world's largest database on nucleotide data. Covers both full genomes and partial fragments. (NCBI is including both GenBank and the Sequence Short Read Archive(SRA))	High	Free Access	Is currently querying all samples, difficult to query for aquatic eDNA.
ENA	True	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home	Globally and taxonomically comprehensive database for nucleotide data including raw data, assembled sequences and annotations.	High	Free Access	Using a Taxonomic & aquatic ENV query (1,700,000)
DDBJ	True	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/index-e.html	DNA Data Bank of Japan. Bioinformatics and DDBJ Center provides sharing and analysis services for data from life science researchers and advanced science.	High	Free Access	Using a Taxonomic & ENV query (1,810,222)
OBIS	False(mainly)	https://obis.org/	Ocean Biodiversity Information System. OBIS accepts DNA-based data; although most users will deposit the primary sequence data in a designated sequence database. Users are encouraged to add the sequence of each ASV in the final ASV table, but it isn't mirrored to other repositories so the raw sequence data would have to be deposited separately	High		19,539,744 Reported on home page of 23,502,158 sequences Searched through the mapper: 19,539,744 records Accessed via https://mapper.obis.org/?hasextensions=DNADerivedData#
GBIF	False(mainly a biodiversity portal)	https://www.gbif.org/	Global Biodiversity Information Facility. GBIF accepts DNA-based data; although most users will deposit the primary sequence data in a designated sequence database.	High		29,296,935 for all sequence records not just aquatic (GBIF's https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/search?advanced=1&is_sequenced=true)

EukBank	False(mainly)	https://zenodo.org/records/7804946	This repository contains the files constituting the first release of the EukBank 18S V4 dataset gathering 12,672 metabarcoding samples globally distributed across biomes for which 335,662 ASVs have been identified. This is not a actual repository, but a dataset in Zenodo, taken as an example of eDNA data in a general purpose repository	High	Free Access	The final database contains 46,345 sequences (1,523 of which are environmental) representing most of the sequenced eukaryotic diversity.
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B. Questionnaire based survey

The results were collated into the eDNA_Survey-Data.xlsx file. 61 questionnaire evaluations were collated covering 109 initiative/repositories.

C. Standardisation of Marker Genes

There is a very little standardisation of Marker Genes Nomenclature in many of the repositories. The advent of HUGO and VGN [Tweedie 2021] provide obvious choices for at least vertebrate gene marker nomenclature.

1. BOLD and Marker Genes

BOLD was not in our eDNA target repository for eDNA, but it is a key part of the eDNA related biodiversity data infrastructure. Notably there is [automated submission of sequence data to NCBI\(Genbank\)](#). In table 5 we have collated some details to allow comparison. Source [7th June 2024]: https://www.boldsystems.org/index.php/TaxBrowser_Home

Animals, plants, fungi and protists.

- Species with Barcodes: 353,585
- Specimens with Barcodes: 17,319,712
- Specimen Records: 22,196,848

Table 5: BOLD BARCODES summary features per barcode gene

https://www.boldsystems.org/index.php/IDS_OpenIdEngine

BARCODE gene	Purpose	Features
CO1	Animal Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Barcode Records on BOLD (14,233,929 Sequences) • Species Level Barcode Records (5,002,263 Sequences/245,590 Species/120,966 Interim Species) • Public Record Barcode Database (2,513,939 Sequences/155,268 Species/69,700 Interim Species)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full Length Record Barcode Database (3,549,672 Sequences/221,409 Species/100,061 Interim Species) • Subset of the Species library with a minimum sequence length of 640bp and containing both public and private records. This library is intended for short sequence identification as it provides maximum overlap with short reads from the barcode region of COI.
ITS	Fungal Identification	(There are very few ITS records on BOLD so most queries will likely not return a successful match.)
RBCL & MAT	Plant identification	(There are very few rbcl and matK records on BOLD so most queries will likely not return a successful match.)

2. INSDC BARCODES

In INSDC there are recommendations of: 16S rRNA, 18S rRNA, 28S rRNA, RBCL, matK, COX1, ITS1-5.8S-ITS2, exome and “other”. However only 2.32% (35,755) 1.5 million aquatic environmental raw sequences had meaningfully named “target_gene” value and only some of those submissions followed these recommendations. Table 6 shows a harmonised version of count of records per target gene. It is ambiguous with 16S to know whether it is rRNA or rDNA, so both are included; this could be deconvoluted in many cases by what taxonomic organisms were determined in MGNify, GBIF etc., which is unnecessarily complex!

Table 6: Target Gene (=barcode) counts in aquatic environmental samples in ENA

target_gene_clean_set	count	percentage
['18S']	15241	45.15%
['16S rRNA']	10565	31.30%
['16S']	4742	14.05%
['COX1']	1325	3.92%
['ITS']	1268	3.76%
['12S']	199	0.59%
['16S rDNA']	192	0.57%
['16S rRNA', '18S']	100	0.30%
['ITS1']	76	0.23%
['ITS2']	31	0.09%
['rbcl']	20	0.06%

However, more of the barcoding genes can be extracted from the studies associated with raw sequence records. These are mainly from the study description, but sometimes from the

study titles. The gene name was harmonised where it was unambiguous. For the studies associated with the raw sequence records over 20% of them mentioned readily identifiable barcode gene(s): present_count=330,632(21.50%) and absent_count=1,207,531(78.50%). The barcode gene(s) are detailed in Table 7, the counts are a sum of the total raw sequence records per “hit” study identifier. Around half of those raw sequence records are associated with 16S rRNA barcodes.

Table 7: Aquatic Environmental raw sequences counts per barcode gene as mentioned in the raw sequences associated study for those records.

barcoding_genes_from_study	count	percentage
['16S rRNA']	144171	43.60%
['16S']	47653	14.41%
['18S']	46074	13.94%
['ITS']	15553	4.70%
['ITS2']	10386	3.14%
['16S rDNA']	9807	2.97%
['16S rRNA', '18S']	8742	2.64%
['ITS', '18S']	6633	2.01%
['ITS1']	6194	1.87%
['COX1', '18S']	4651	1.41%
['16S rRNA', 'ITS']	4375	1.32%
['COX1']	4306	1.30%
['16S rRNA', '12S']	2664	0.81%
['12S']	2557	0.77%
['ITS1', 'ITS', 'ITS2', 'COX1', '18S']	2070	0.63%
['ITS1', '16S rRNA']	1863	0.56%
['16S rDNA', '16S rRNA']	986	0.30%
['ITS2', '16S rRNA']	917	0.28%
['ITS1', 'ITS']	911	0.28%
['18S', 'COX1', 'rbcL']	896	0.27%

The obvious observation is that one needs to search the study information to find out which barcode genes the raw sequences were analysed for, this is non-trivial. I.E. There are multiple gaps within the INSDC archives: the barcode gene nomenclature is inconsistent, they are usually not recorded in the “target_genes” metadata field and only 20% even record them within the study information. Note, that as with the taxonomy, the interpretation of the

barcode data is not done with the raw sequence deposition in INSDC, but is in resources such as [MGnify](#), OBIS and GBIF.

3. Barcodes from the eDNA Questionnaire Survey

For the questionnaire survey data, barcodes had been harmonised and reported as “Markers_Simplified”. The more established marker counts are shown in Table 8 and Figure 4, this includes “Metagenome” and “Metatranscriptome” strategies too. There were also some interesting entries in this field, all just reported once: *cyrA*, *sxtI*, *anaC*, *anaF*, *cyrJ*, *cyrB*, *cyrC*, *sxtG*, *pca*, *sxtH*, *mcyF*, *sxtA*, *mcyG*, *mcyE*, *mcyD*, *mcyC*, *mcyB*, *mcyA*, TROLL. Many of the latter are genes encoding for enzymes in marine and freshwater cyanobacteria see [Gaget 2022]).

Table 8: Frequency of harmonised markers (“Markers_Simplified”) reported in the questionnaire survey for more well established markers.

barcode	count	barcode_species
18S_rRNA	37	nematodes and many microeukaryotes
16S_rRNA	35	bacteria
COX1	30	invertebrates, vertebrates
ITS1-5.8S-ITS2	17	fungi
12S_rRNA	17	fish, amphibians
rbcl	11	diatoms/plants
Metagenome	2	
mtDNA_ControlRegion	1	
Cytb	1	fish
23S_rRNA	1	microalgae / algae
28S_rRNA	1	Protists

Figure 4: Counts of different markers recorded in the questionnaire survey

Survey: Aquatic :Markers_Simplified

E. LLM results

A Large Language Model (LLM) was used to automatically analyse text of the biological papers found on the Internet. In this deliverable it was used to answer the following questions:

1. Is the data available in paper or supplement?
2. What is the sample collection method?
3. What is the DNA extraction method?
4. What is the source of the protocol in protocols.io?
5. What is the overall sequencing strategy used in experiment?
6. What is the sequence analysis workflow?
7. Where is the data stored?

LLM was able to process 1440 papers (out of 1607 downloaded with crawler). The dataset contains the DOI number of downloaded publications, title, full content of the paper, content of the paragraphs (not for all papers), information if the paper is on eDNA data and the responses for the questions that LLM responded to. All the attributes are text data apart from eDNA info which is logical value. Full database with the results from LLM is accessible in https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Gk7EBMkEr0_iJCFXTMzlvukFAKjYwP1G/view?usp=drive_link

4. Deeper Analysis

There are different ways we could have approached the analysis of the various sources. The analysis below is firstly for the eDNA “bioinformatics” inventory in a general way. There is then analysis aiming to answer the main items we were tasked with. That is taken from this eDNA “bioinformatics” inventory (details about INSDC (via ENA), details from OBIS) and much about the questionnaire survey results. Finally the LLM results are analysed.

A. Bioinformatics eDNA Inventory Findings

These are broader findings from the bioinformatics inventory. We have grouped them in categories to aid the interpretation and digestibility.

1. eDNA Inventory: Database profile (db_profile) Category

Apart from EukBank, all the repositories are active and at least annually updated (Table 10). All the repositories apart from OBIS are used by both the marine and freshwater communities. All of the repositories, arguably apart from Mitofish, have some degree of curation to improve the quality of the metadata. Note in the INSDC, much of this is automated curation, e.g. if using synonyms, rather than manual curation. One example of this is that the assigned taxonomy of the INSDC raw sequence is what the submitter provides to the sample and this is often by taxonomic identification in the case of eDNA, but taxonomy is not then curated.

Table 10: eDNA inventory - database profile (db_profile) summary for the seven repositories.

Repository	DB active?	Curation?	usage	Using community	Annually updated?	Contains env data?
ENA	True	True	100	mixed	True	True
DDB J	True	True	100	mixed	True	True
NCBI	True	True	100	mixed	True	True
OBIS	True	True	?	only marine water	True	True

GBIF	True	True	? For biodiversity users will be high	mixed	True	True
EukBank	False	True	0	mixed	False	True
Mitofish	True	False	nan	mixed	True	False

2. eDNA Inventory: Database size (db_size) Category

The number of records per database varies massively (Table 11). In the case of the INSDC repositories, as they share almost all raw sequence records the totals should be similar. The discrepancy found was due to the fact that for ENA and DDBJ we were querying for aquatic environmental raw sequence records, but we did not do similar filtering for NCBI during the inventorying phase, although it is possible. Nevertheless we estimate that there are in the magnitude of 1.5 million INSDC aquatic eDNA raw sequence records; one or several raw sequence records will be from the same environmental sample. A similar magnitude of eDNA raw sequence records (1 million) was observed for Mitofish which is surprising. OBIS and GBIF both had in the magnitude of 30 million records, although GBIF's aquatic records will only be a subset of this. Also to note that GBIF records are not raw sequences, but occurrences derived from processed sequences, where several may derive from a single raw sequence record. Similarly for OBIS, there is in fact only a very limited amount of eDNA present, it is mainly processed DNA, but it was not possible for the people inventorying this to ascertain. EukBank is relatively small with just under 50,000 records and these are processed sequence records. Our investigation showed how difficult it is to get reliable counts of eDNA. There are thus some obvious questions here about just how many eDNA aquatic raw sequence records there are, and why they are not in the primary archives [Hassenrück 2002, Jurburg 2020].

Table 11: eDNA inventory - database size (db_size) summary for the seven repositories.

Repository	record total	number of records (scaled)
ENA	1,500,000	2 million

DDBJ	1,810,222	2 million
NCBI	42,559,4654	40 million
OBIS	23,502,158	25 million
GBIF	29,295,455	30 million
EukBank	46,345	0.05 million
Mitofish	843,537	1 million

3. eDNA Inventory: Sample details (sample_details) Category

Apart from Mitofish all the repositories had at least some records with GPS coordinates and also the sample collection (Table 12). The GPS coordinates constitute very relevant information, as it is an interoperability gateway to and from so much other information. There are also many other sample metadata captured in the repositories.

Table 12: eDNA Inventory: sample_details summary for the seven repositories.

Repository	GPS_coordinates_available	sample_collection
ENA	True	True
DDBJ	True	True
NCBI	True	True

OBIS	True	True
GBIF	True	True
EukBank	True	True
Mitofish	False	False

4. eDNA Inventory: Barcode Category

We believe that all of the eDNA resources beside GBIFs, capture barcode marker names (Table 13). Only OBIS has barcode certainty. We think that the barcode taxonomy confidence values in the spreadsheet are not correct for the INSDC, as the taxonomy is determined by what the submitter puts at the sample level.

Table 13: eDNA Inventory: barcode summary for the seven repositories.

Repository	barcode_certain	barcode_name	barcode_taxonomy_confidence
ENA	False	True	True
DDBJ	False	True	True
NCBI	False	True	True
OBIS	True	True	True
GBIF	False	FALSE (But uses Barcode Index Numbers (BINs))	False

EukBank	False	private	True
Mitofish	False	mtDNA	False

5. eDNA Inventory: Taxonomy Category

All the resources identify the records with solid taxonomy names and identifiers, mainly using the NCBI taxonomy or WoRMS (Table 14). (Note that the INSDC db's only know the taxonomy of the sample not of the analysed results.) OBIS is the only resource with a taxonomy_URL.

Table 14: eDNA Inventory: Taxonomy summary for the seven repositories.

Repository	taxonomical_name	taxonomically_identified	taxonomy_URL	taxonomy_linking	taxonomy_origin
ENA	True	True	False	True	NCBI
DDBJ	True	True	False	True	NCBI
NCBI	True	True	False	True	NCBI
OBIS	True	True	True	True	WoRMS Aphiald
GBIF	True	True	False	True	GBIF Backbone Taxonomy (With the values going into from 105 taxonomic sources e.g. EOL, NCBI/GenBank or IUCN)

EukBank	True	True	https://zenodo.org/records/6896896	False	EukRibo, ENA
Mitofish	True	True	nan	True	NCBI

6. eDNA Inventory: experiment_metadata Category

The experiment sequencing strategy and methodology are captured consistently in all the repositories apart from GBIF and Mitofish (Table 15). The DNA extraction follows the same repository pattern, but is less consistently captured. Analysis workflows are typically only captured in OBIS and EukBank. eDNA data needs to be published to OBIS with an Occurrence Core table + DNADeriveddata extension table (from https://manual.obis.org/darwin_core.html).

Table 15: eDNA Inventory: experiment metadata summary for the 7 repositories.

Repository	DNA_extraction	analysis_workflow	sequence_methodology	sequencing_strategy
ENA	True	False	True	True
DDBJ	True	False	True	True
NCBI	True	False	True	True
OBIS	True	True	True	True
GBIF	False	False	False	False
EukBank	True	True	True	True

Mitofish	False	False	False	False
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7. eDNA Inventory: Sequence Related Category

In terms of the type of eDNA sequence data, the INSDC archives mostly contain raw sequences (primary status) (Table 16). The other repositories contain mostly processed sequences (secondary status).

Table 16: eDNA Inventory: Sequence Related summary for the seven repositories.

Repository	Primary/Secondary	directly_uploaded	sequences_processed
ENA	Primary	True	both
DDBJ	Primary	True	both
NCBI	Primary	True	both
OBIS	Secondary	True	processed
GBIF	Secondary	True	processed
EukBank	Secondary	False	processed
Mitofish	Secondary	False	both

8. eDNA Inventory: data_access Category

Apart from EukBank, all repositories had APIs, URLs and a web interface. None had a standalone desktop application.

Table 17: eDNA Inventory: Data Access summary for the seven repositories.

Repository	API	application	record_URL	web_interface
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ENA	True	False	True	True
DDBJ	True	False	True	True
NCBI	True	False	True	True
OBIS	True	False	True	True
GBIF	True	False	True	True
EukBank	False	False	False	False
Mitofish	True	True	True	True

9. eDNA Inventory: General Metadata Category

This category is a grouping about general metadata properties (Table 18). We observed that most repositories had both minimal mandatory metadata and imposed database standards, with the possible exception of EukBank for mandatory metadata and MitoFish for a defined format. Just the INSDC DBs were observed to have a clear data and metadata link in the inventory.

Table 18: eDNA Inventory: General Metadata summary for the seven repositories.

Repository	DB mandatory metadata	DB standard consistent	A link to between the data and metadata
ENA	at least a minimum amount of metadata	1	Yes, eDNA raw sequence has minimal metadata and links to biosamples metadata and to study metadata.
DDBJ	at least a minimum amount of metadata	1	Yes, eDNA raw sequence has minimal metadata and links to biosamples metadata and to study metadata.
NCBI	at least a minimum amount of metadata	1	Yes, eDNA raw sequence has minimal metadata and links to biosamples metadata and to study metadata. Based on biosample database there are some meta data e.g. sample name AN-C-c2-56d; collection date 2018; depth not applicable; broad-scale environmental context contaminated water; local-scale environmental context environmental contaminant; environmental medium groundwater; geographic location not applicable; latitude and longitude not applicable;

			project name Analysis of sequences collected from groundwater culture
OBIS	Yes minimum terms for either core(event or occurrence)	1	Sampling metadata are given in the occurrence data table alongside the occurrence record (ASV/species name, read abundance). The records are linked by the occurrenceID to the dnaderiveddata table with molecular/experimental metadata
GBIF	Yes, but there are 3 different data standards/formats which data could be deposited in. These range from Darwin Core(mandatory: occurrenceID, basisOfRecord, scientificName, eventDate), to Access to Biological Collections Data schema (ABCD) which does have a limited number of mandatory fields https://github.com/tdwg/wiki-archive/blob/master/twiki/data/ABCD/AbcdPrimer.txt	1	occurrenceID
EukBank	nan	1	Yes. csv files connected with IDs
Mitofish	taxonomy, water area, habitat, depth range, importance for Fisheries, Threat to Humans, IUCN Red List Status	nan	Yes. Limited information related to sequence and species

10. eDNA Inventory: metadata_format Category

The metadata formats are quite variable, the most consistent are the OBIS and GBIF with the Darwin-Core (Table 19).

Table 19: eDNA Inventory: metadata_format summary for the seven repositories.

Repository	metadata_export_format	metadata_file_format
ENA	xml, csv	Upload through interface / programmatically with XML
DDBJ	xml, csv	nan
NCBI	nan	for SRA, you have to complete the MIMARCKs excel file and then upload that to the website.

OBIS	CSV,parquet	Darwin-Core-A
GBIF	JSON	Yes, TDWG Darwin core preferred, here is the full list: https://www.tdwg.org/standards/ . (Access to Biological Collection Data (ABCD) Schema, Audiovisual Core Multimedia Resources Metadata Schema, Authors of Plant Names, Botanico-Periodicum-Huntianum, Botanico-Periodicum-Huntianum/Supplementum, Darwin Core, Description Language for Taxonomy (DELTA), Economic Botany Data Collection Standard, Floristic Regions of the World, GUID and Life Sciences Identifiers Applicability Statements, Herbarium Information Standards and Protocols for Interchange of Data (HISPID3), Index Herbariorum. Part I: The Herbaria of the World, International Transfer Format for Botanic Garden Plant Records (ITF2), Plant Names in Botanical Databases, Plant Occurrence and Status Scheme (POSS), Structured Descriptive Data (SDD), Taxon Concept Schema (TCS), Taxonomic Literature, Edition 2 and its Supplements (TL-2), TDWG Access Protocol for Information Retrieval (TAPIR), TDWG Standards Documentation Standard (SDS), Vocabulary Maintenance Standard (VMS), World Geographical Scheme for Recording Plant Distributions (WGSRPD), XDF - A Language for the Definition and Exchange of Biological Data Sets)
EukBank	csv	nan
Mitofish	nan	nan

11. eDNA Inventory: data_format

For sequence and metadata there is a variety of data formats (table 20). Sequences are generally available in either fasta or fastq format. For the rest of the data, it is unclear as to what format that would be, however as most offered an API the data will be retrievable in a structured format. The gap here is inconsistency of data formats besides fasta (variable) and fastq.

Table 20: eDNA Inventory: data_format summary for the seven repositories.

	data_export_format	data_file_format
ENA	fasta,fastq	nan

DDBJ	fasta,fastq	nan
NCBI	fasta,fastq	fasta,fastq
OBIS	CSV,parquet DwC-A file (occurrence.txt and dnaderiveddata.txt)	
GBIF	JSON	nan
EukBank	csv	nan
Mitofish	fasta, annotated fasta, text	There is no option to upload data to database, but there is a web site interface to search (blast) own sequence against database

12. eDNA Inventory: publication

The repositories that seem to handle publication the best for aquatic eDNA processed sequences are OBIS, GBIF, and EukBank (Table 21). The INSDC manages publication ids reasonably well too, but these are attached to the study not specific samples or sequence records.

Table 21: eDNA Inventory: publication summary for the seven repositories.

	data_paper_location	paper_Doi_number	paper_link
ENA	nan	False	0

DDBJ	nan	False	0
NCBI	nan	False	0
OBIS	False	True	1
GBIF	False	True	1
EukBank	main	True	1
Mitofish	nan	False	nan

B. General Analysis: Bioinformatics Inventory and the Survey

1. Proportion of data INSDC repositories

From the necessary queries, it is difficult to get all environmental samples from INSDC databases. On the positive side there are many relevant records > 4 million environmental raw sequences; this does include both terrestrial and aquatic.

Aquatic Environmental DNA in INSDC

The INSDC has 1.5 million (1,538,163) raw sequence records [September 2024] that are associated with aquatic eDNA samples. Table 22 shows where the aquatic eDNA records were submitted to.

Table 22: Number of records submitted to each of the INSDC databases

insdc_member_receiver	count	percentage
NCBI	1052806	68.45%
ENA	475981	30.94%
DDBJ	9376	0.61%

Figure 5 represents the cumulative count of aquatic raw sequence data submitted to INSDC. Although it is a log plot there appears to be a relevant decrease in rate of submissions, the last few years were disrupted by the pandemic.

Figure 5: Plot of the aquatic read_run sequence record cumulative count

Studies, Sample Checklists and Raw Sequence Objects

Data is submitted to INSDC archives at different data object levels, the most relevant to environmental data are:

1. study (bioproject)
2. sample level (biosamples)
3. raw sequence (the sequence and experimental metadata)

There is some, albeit limited control of metadata at all levels. The data submission order is 1 through 3. For our eDNA purposes we can make use of the metadata at all these levels to gain more insight into data.

Samples are submitted to INSDC using sample checklists/packages. Each sample checklist/package is there to be broadly tuned to a category of samples. These sample checklists/packages have mandatory, recommended and optional metadata fields. There are many different environmental checklists/packages, many of these are based on the [GSC MIXs](#).

Bias

Note: There is bias towards finding marine rather than freshwater for three main reasons:

1. precision is needed for a lat/lon coordinate to be located in freshwater shapefiles, so challenging besides very large lakes or rivers.
2. oceans and seas are often recorded in a country's name metadata, other regions less so.
3. WoRMS is focused on marine organisms. The biome (broad_scale_environmental_context) field is particularly useful for freshwater though.

2. Proportion instruments and Platforms used in INSDC and the Survey Initiatives

The instrument and platform data were not explicitly captured during the bioinformatics inventorying of the eDNA archives. We had determined these for INSDC via ENA (see section 2.C). Useful instrument and platform data were also captured in the survey (section 2.D). The results are comparable hence are shown together.

1. INSDC: Sequencing Platforms and Instruments

From the INSDC, the bulk of the DB's are using shorter read high throughput sequencers, with a significant fraction of long read (e.g. PacBio and Ion Torrent) with a small amount of old sequencing technologies (Table 23, Figure 6, 7). The platform and instrument values are well controlled and populated in the INSDC archives.

Figure 6 shows that the majority of libraries are either amplicon or WGS. It also clearly illustrates that the prokaryotic community is mainly using WGS, while for eukaryotes more than half of the records come from amplicon sequencing. WGS is also well represented for eukaryotes.

In Figure 7, we can see that a variety of NGS platforms is being used, albeit dominated by Illumina (was Solexa). The figure also shows the emergence of long read platforms, and the massive growth in sequencing relevant to the aquatic environment.

Table 23: INSDC Aquatic environmental samples sequencing platform

instrument_platform	record_count
ILLUMINA	1451773
LS454	30802
ION_TORRENT	17037
PACBIO_SMRT	10894
OXFORD_NANOPORE	9759
DNBSEQ	8184
CAPILLARY	4107
BGISEQ	3876
ABI_SOLID	1502
ELEMENT	131
HELICOS	45
COMPLETE_GENOMICS	30
ULTIMA	23

Figure 6: Sankey plot showing the relationship between the key mandatory experiment sequence metadata (instrument and library) and taxonomy for our filtered aquatic dataset.

Figure 7: Sankey plot showing the relationship between the key mandatory experiment sequence metadata (library_source, library_strategy, platform and collection dates) for our filtered aquatic dataset.

2. Questionnaire survey data: Sequencing Platforms and Instruments

From the survey, the bulk of the DB's are using shorter read high throughput sequencers, with a significant fraction of long read (e.g. Nanopore and Ion Torrent) with a small amount of old sequencing technologies (Table 24).

Table 24: Survey Sequencing platforms and Instrumentation

instrument	count
Illumina_MiSeq	47
Illumina_NovaSeq	16
Illumina_HiSeq	19
Illumina_NextSeq	8
IonTorrent_PGM	3
Roche_454	7
Nanopore_ONT	10
PacBio_Sequel	4
Unknown_Unknown	2
ABI_3130(Sanger)	1
IonTorrent_S5	1

Illumina_NextStep	1
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3. Proportion of repositories frozen or whether new data was still being collected.

For the bioinformatics inventory EukBank was the only frozen repository and this data was derived from data available at INSDC. There was no data in the survey results, to determine whether those initiatives were active or frozen in terms of data being collected.

4. Geographic information

Proportions of Records with Latitude and Longitude in INSDC

In INSDC, over 72% of the worldwide aquatic environment raw sequence records are associated with latitude and longitude coordinates (for aquatic environments) (Table 25). For Europe this is over 84% and consistent for freshwater(~country) and seas around Europe. This is an important and exciting observation as once these coordinates are known many other environmental e.g. oceanographic data, can be aggregated to it. A caveat is that the data may be biased, as information derived from coordinates was one of the selection criteria for the aquatic environment subset.

Table 25: Proportion of ENA aquatic environments raw sequence records having latitude and longitude coordinates

	Has geographical coordinates	count	percentage
Whole world	True	1,112,710	72.34%
Whole world	False	425,453	27.66%
Europe (countries and seas)	True	135,069	84.53%
Europe (countries and seas)	False	24,715	15.47%
Europe(countries)	True	120,599	84.51%
Europe(countries)	False	22,112	15.49%
Europe(seas)	True	14,470	84.75%
Europe(seas)	False	2,603	15.25%

eDNA in INSDCby Countries: firstly world, then Europe, then Oceans.

It is clear that by country, the majority of aquatic eDNA is from the USA and China, European countries together have contributed a smaller magnitude to each of these (Tables 25 and 26,

Figure 8-10). The “missing” country entities will reduce over time, as since 2023 the INSDC has had a mandatory spatiotemporal policy, this will increase the labelled oceans too. It is notable that large areas of the world are having little freshwater eDNA data being reported in INSDC, especially Africa and South America.

Table 26: top 20 countries in aquatic eDNA raw sequence records counts at INSDC.

country_clean	count	percentage
United States of America	353841	23.00%
missing	339131	22.05%
China	286658	18.64%
Australia	92176	5.99%
Canada	35514	2.31%
Pacific Ocean	35167	2.29%
United Kingdom	26092	1.70%
Brazil	20968	1.36%
Atlantic Ocean	14927	0.97%
Germany	12896	0.84%
France	12488	0.81%
Sweden	11285	0.73%
Spain	10300	0.67%
Mexico	9732	0.63%
Singapore	9647	0.63%
South Korea	9643	0.63%
New Zealand	9071	0.59%
Norway	8961	0.58%
Baltic Sea	7172	0.47%
Denmark	6681	0.43%

Figure 10: Aquatic eDNA in INSDC, read_run record frequency in Europe.

For the survey a similar analysis of database responses and counties was performed (Table 27 and Figure 11). Here we collated the databases by reported county and seas(as a single entity). It does show the bias with respect to which organisations responded to the survey, so we are seeing an over representation of Iberian countries, but an under representation of countries with often higher research budgets like Germany, France, Italy and UK. Nevertheless, we can see at least some coverage of most of western, northern and southern Europe.

Table 27: eDNA Survey by country of coverage

country	count
sea(European)	12
Portugal	10
Spain	5
Europe	4
Sweden	4
Greece	4
Norway	4
France	3
Germany	2
Slovakia	2
Poland	2
French	1

Switzerland	1
Sicily	1
Finland	1
Netherlands	1
Belgium	1
United Kingdom	1
Georgia	1
Iberia	1
Italy	1
Malta	1

Figure 11: Aquatic eDNA survey record frequency

Marine counts for INSDC raw sequence, Worldwide and just Europe

We analysed the seas and oceans in the “geo_loc” field for the INSDC environmental aquatic raw sequence worldwide (Table 28) and seas bordering Europe (Table 29). For the European analysis slightly we additionally did a more exhaustive text mining match for European Seas, hence one can see a higher count for Mediterranean Seas for example.

As expected the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans are the most sampled. A surprise to us was the higher number of eDNA sequences submitted from the Baltic, than the Mediterranean Sea.

Table 28: INSDC Aquatic raw sequence count by Oceans

ocean	count	percentage
Pacific Ocean	35167	43.28%
Atlantic Ocean	14927	18.37%
Baltic Sea	7172	8.83%
North Sea	5136	6.32%
Indian Ocean	5102	6.28%
Arctic Ocean	4974	6.12%
Mediterranean Sea	4749	5.84%
Southern Ocean	3308	4.07%
Tasman Sea	435	0.54%
Coral Sea Islands	202	0.25%
Ross Sea	90	0.11%

Table 29: INSDC Aquatic eDNA raw sequences in European Seas

europaean_sea	count	percentage
Baltic Sea	8195	37.80%
Mediterranean Sea	6245	28.80%
North Sea	5435	25.07%
Adriatic Sea	346	1.60%
Black Sea	343	1.58%
Bay Of Biscay	336	1.55%
English Channel	197	0.91%
North Atlantic Ocean	134	0.62%
Barents Sea	127	0.59%
White Sea	107	0.49%
Ionian Sea	105	0.48%
Caspian Sea	45	0.21%
Norwegian Sea	31	0.14%
Kattegat	19	0.09%
Irish Sea	12	0.06%

North-east Atlantic Ocean	4	0.02%
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Freshwater Types counts for INSDC raw sequence: Worldwide and just Europe

We used several different metadata sources to determine the freshwater type, both worldwide (Table 30) and in Europe (Table 31). Note: there is an element of noise here, achieved by regex of broadscale_environment_category or from geographical region, metadata. Lake is the freshwater environment of the majority of the raw sequence records, followed by river and a long tale of other freshwater environments, with a similar pattern worldwide and in Europe . Even worldwide it is surprising how few raw sequence records were from springs or streams (902).

Table 30: Freshwater types worldwide counts and percentage in INSDC raw sequence records.

freshwater_type	count	percentage
lake	20177	49.89%
river	14861	36.74%
reservoir	1954	4.83%
pond	943	2.33%
wetland	880	2.18%
bog	534	1.32%
stream	465	1.15%
spring	437	1.08%
canal	127	0.31%
freshwater_sediment	68	0.17%

Table 31: Freshwater type counts and percentages in Europe in INSDC raw sequence records.

freshwater_type	count	percentage
lake	8321	68.40%
river	1652	13.58%
groundwater	611	5.02%
stream	509	4.18%
reservoir	318	2.61%
wetland	194	1.59%
pond	168	1.38%

bog	109	0.90%
freshwater_sediment	105	0.86%
spring	87	0.72%
drinking_water	56	0.46%
canal	36	0.30%

As detailed in the 2.C section “Filtering for Aquatic eDNA in ENA”, determining aquatic raw sequence records was mainly done using the ENA geo_tags and env_tags. These group records in seven broad environment categories (Table 32). The confidence (env_confidence) was predicted based on the evidence gathered from the different tagging systems, e.g. conflicting tags reducing the confidence. This is however, still a very rough approximation of confidence. The results show that some of coarsely filtered “aquatic” samples are not aquatic. Some of the terrestrial records may be freshwater, as it is often hard to systematically detect these with enough accuracy given the method used for labelling (see section 2.C). The “mixed_aquatic” records in Table 32 correspond to those where one can’t reliably distinguish between marine, freshwater, coastal and brackish and “mixed” correspond to those where a record could be aquatic or terrestrial. As the table 32 and figure 12 show, that they are collectively a significant fraction of the records. What can be taken from the analysis though, is that there is a broad coverage of aquatic environment types.

Table 32: Aquatic Environmental eDNA in INSDC

env_prediction	env_confidence	count
brackish	low	2795
brackish	medium	560
coastal	high	93597
coastal	medium	84655
freshwater	low	512949
freshwater	medium	19807
marine	high	113981
marine	low	7
marine	medium	160779
mixed	low	74680
mixed_aquatic	low	216616
mixed_aquatic	medium	21982
terrestrial	high	133359
terrestrial	medium	97599

terrestrial_assumed	low	4797
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Figure 12: INSDC aquatic raw sequence environmental predictions using species + lat/long. The mixed aquatic is where there was conflicting or ambiguous metadata, but the records were aquatic.

The above tables of analysed data provide relevant information about the numbers of records from different ecological environments. In Figure 12 and Table 28, for example, we can see the proportions of INSDC “aquatic” raw sequence records in different aquatic environments, with a varied “confidence” in the assertions. We have a diverse ecological origin of the samples, from marine, to coastal and freshwater in significant proportions. For a small proportion (table 26 and 27) there is detailed environmental information often captured by ENVO ontology terms/ids. Some cannot be unambiguously determined even to a high level aquatic domain(mixed and mixed_aquatic). For those asserted to be terrestrial many indeed may be aquatic samples, but the metadata available does not contain enough resolution to accurately determine it.

5. Survey/Questionnaire: Environments

The survey’s database provided a list of the main types of aquatic environments that the eDNA data is being deposited to (Table 33). The marine environment is the most frequently reported, the freshwater environment only slightly less, whilst 15 DBs cover transitional environments (coastal, estuary, brackish=transitional) and just 2 for groundwater. The DB’s are thus covering a representative cross section of the major European aquatic environmental types.

Table 33: Survey DB proportions of aquatic environment types

Environment	Count
Marine	37
Freshwater	31
Transitional	15

Groundwater	2
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Figure 13: Survey DB proportions of aquatic environment types i) broad aquatic type and ii) detailed environment

6. Taxonomic Coverage

INSDC(including ENA) has coverage of the whole spectrum of taxonomy, if such eDNA raw sequences were deposited by the science community. Tables 34 and Figure 14, are showing the eDNA counts by a taxonomy value for all species; the taxonomic value chosen is two

steps back in the taxonomic hierarchy from the submitted taxonomic record (this was arbitrary). Tables 35 is on eukaryotes and Table 36 on mammals. If we were to mine through all associated GBIF/MGnify etc. records where taxonomic calls had been made, we would see the true taxonomic coverage. Nevertheless, we can see representation from across superkingdoms. It is gratifying to see ecological metagenomes as over 40% of entries for this aquatic, environment filtered collection of eDNA raw sequence records.

Table 34: Raw sequence counts of environmental aquatic eDNA per taxonomy

lineage_minus2	count	percentage
ecological metagenomes	602351	40.43%
organismal metagenomes	400852	26.91%
Saccharomyces	140005	9.40%
metagenomes	79062	5.31%
Anopheles	70596	4.74%
environmental samples	20462	1.37%
Vibrio	13218	0.89%
Salmo	12283	0.82%
Toxoplasma	7646	0.51%
Plasmodium (Laverania)	7058	0.47%
Gasterosteus	5737	0.39%
Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus	5153	0.35%
Bacillus	3888	0.26%
Eukaryota	3457	0.23%
Arabidopsis	3433	0.23%
Bacteria	3110	0.21%
Oncorhynchus	3008	0.20%
Oryzias	2958	0.20%
Pan	2763	0.19%
Ciona	2689	0.18%

Figure 14: INSDC aquatic records, with the most informative taxonomic lineage fields

Table 35: In INSDC these are the most common eukaryotic (NCBI taxid:2759) high level “taxonomic” lineages in the aquatic environment records (see Figure 14)

lineage_minus2	count	percentage
ecological metagenomes	611159	39.75%
organismal metagenomes	407626	26.51%
Saccharomyces	140005	9.10%
metagenomes	79062	5.14%
Anopheles	70596	4.59%
environmental samples	21132	1.37%
Vibrio	13436	0.87%
Salmo	12283	0.80%
Bacteria	9219	0.60%
Toxoplasma	7646	0.50%
Plasmodium (Laverania)	7058	0.46%
Gasterosteus	5737	0.37%

For aquatic vertebrates (see Figure 15) Salmon and trout dominated the records, closely followed by ray-finned fishes and rice fishes (*Oryzias* - fresh and brackish water). There were also strong numbers of domesticated livestock, though these may be due to contamination. The relatively high presence of chimpanzees is harder to explain. Of relevance however, is that in the INSDC databases the identification of the species present within raw sequence records is not usually recorded, this information will be associated with processed sequences in DBs like GBIF.

Figure 15: INSDC aquatic records, with the most informative taxonomic lineage fields for vertebrates.

C. Survey: General Sample and Sequencing Related Metadata

The Survey data very usefully captures general information about the types of metadata present in the surveyed metadata. Total db collections = 61, total collections with metadata types recorded = 41, collections without metadata = 20.

Table 36 shows the frequency of each metadata type. Figure 16 illustrates how often two types of metadata co-occur in the same database, displayed by edge weight.

So we can see that “GPS_Coordinates” and “Sampling_Date” both occur frequently and together, whereas Molecular_Markers and Sequencing_Platform occur less frequently. It should be noted however that the Sequencing instrument is captured elsewhere, so the platform can usually be inferred. Sampling_Location is only occasionally present, but that is not a gap as GPS coordinates usually allow increased utility. Possibly the largest gap is that one third of collections had no such metadata types record.

Table 36: Survey data - Metadata types captured and frequency

Processed_Metadata	count
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GPS_Coordinates	41
Sampling_Date	37
Substrate	31
Sampling_Method	31
DNA_Extraction	31
Markers&Primers	31
Environmental_Data	28
Sequencing_Protocols	26
Bioinformatic_Pipeline	24
Date	3
Sampling_Location	2
Molecular_Markers	2
Sequencing_Platform	2
Taq_Used	1
Physiochemical_Parameters	1

Figure 16: Survey: co-occurrence frequency of metadata types captured.

Figure: survey "Processed_Metadata" frequency co-occurrence graph

Survey: Processed Metadata Standards

Of the 61 DBs of the survey, 41 had no stated processed metadata standards (Table 37). Of those that did, the majority(14) used the Darwin Core standard and a minority GSC MIMARKS(4). Lack of metadata standards of processed metadata standards for these DBs is an important gap.

Table 37: Survey data: Processed Metadata Standards

Processed_MetadataStandard_Structure	count
Darwin_Core	13
MIMARKS	3
Unknown	2
Darwin_Core;MIMARKS	1
MGnify	1

Figure 17: Survey: the processed metadata standards most used.

Survey: Aquatic :Processed_MetadataStandard_Structure

D. LLM: Analysis of Scientific Literature

Question 1. Is the data available in paper or supplement?

Answer for this question indicates where authors of the publication put the reference to the data. It is worth mentioning that we did not specify what kind of data we expected so the LLM had to find the reference to any data generated in experiments. There were 915 papers with data placed in the supplement, 459 papers with data placed in the text and 66 papers where data was placed both in supplement and in the text. The LLM was able to give the proper response for all of 1,440 papers.

Question 2. What is the sample collection method?

Here we are expecting the overall sample collection method based on the papers that the LLM analysed. It was able to process only 1,182 papers due to cut off responses shorter than 150 characters. The responses shorter than that contained too little information to be included in further analysis. The responses of appropriate length were combined into a list and processed by LLM that was asked to provide the overall sample collection method (exact command: based on the provided list, write overall sample collection method). The LLM responded indicating following methods:

- Surveys and interviews
- Filtration devices (VigiBOAT, SPYGEN)
- Microscopic examination
- Kick seining
- Fishing using a boat-mounted electrofishing unit
- Flowthrough columns packed with sieved sediment
- Windshield splatter analysis

It also made a notice that samples in analysed papers were collected using various methods and that it answered based on the context of the provided text.

Question 3. What is the DNA extraction method?

Similarly to the above question, the expected answer was the overall DNA extraction method. Here, the LLM was able to process 946 papers due to excluding responses shorter than 150 characters because of lack of information in it. The approach to the problem was identical to the previous question and the LLM responded in a more expected way than previously. The answer from the LLM is:

The DNA extraction method used in the study involves the following steps:

1. *Sample Preparation: The sample is prepared by homogenizing or grinding the tissue using a mortar and pestle, blender, or other similar tools.*
2. *Lysis: The sample is then treated with a lysis buffer containing detergents and/or enzymes to break down the cell membranes and release the DNA.*
3. *DNA Purification: The released DNA is then purified using a variety of techniques, such as centrifugation, filtration, or precipitation with ethanol or isopropanol.*
4. *Quantification: The quantity of DNA is measured using a spectrophotometer or fluorescence-based assay to determine the amount of DNA available for analysis.*

5. *PCR Setup: The purified DNA is then ready for PCR amplification, which involves the use of primers specific to the target gene regions to amplify the DNA sequences of interest.*

It's worth noting that different methods may be used depending on the specific requirements of the experiment, such as the type of sample, the target organisms, and the desired sensitivity and specificity. Additionally, there are commercial kits available that simplify the DNA extraction process and improve the yield and purity of the extracted DNA.

Question 4. What is the source of the protocol in protocols.io?

Here we want to know the DOI of a protocol used in the paper that was published in protocols.io service. The problem is that it is very rare that researchers publish their protocols. From 1440 analysed papers in only 6 of them was it mentioned that the protocol was placed in protocols.io. The LLM was not able to find any information on this topic so we did it manually by looking for the *protocols.io* phrase in the whole content of the paper. Then the sentence containing this phrase was extracted and we manually extracted the protocol DOI number. Here is the list of all founded DOIs:

- <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n2udgew>
- <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.p9qdr3w>
- <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.u6zezf6>
- <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.hdmb246>
- <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kqdg36261q25/v2>
- <https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.5qpvorkj7v4o/v1>

It is noteworthy that none of these DOIs were listed in the references section of the papers.

Question 5. What is the overall sequencing strategy used in experiment?

This question is similar to questions 2 and 3. The LLM was able to provide responses for 1,425 papers for the same reason as mentioned questions. Here LLM answered very generally. It generated the following steps in sequencing:

1. *DNA extraction.*
2. *PCR amplification.*
3. *Sequencing.*
4. *Bioinformatic data processing.*
5. *Downsampling.*
6. *Taxonomical identification.*
7. *Statistical data analysis.*

Question 6. What is the sequence analysis workflow?

Similar question to question above, but now we are asking about the analysis workflow. Here the LLM was able to respond on 1,438 papers. 2 papers were removed due to responses shorter than 150 characters. LLM indicated following steps as necessary to analyse the data:

1. *Preprocessing: The raw sequencing data is preprocessed to remove low-quality reads, filter out primer sequences and adapter contamination, and extract the relevant features.*
2. *Feature extraction: The remaining high-quality reads are then converted into feature matrices, where each sample is represented as a vector of features.*
3. *Similarity calculation: The similarity between each pair of sequences is calculated based on their features, using techniques such as Euclidean distance or cosine similarity.*
4. *Clustering: The sequences are then grouped into clusters based on their similarities, using techniques such as k-means or hierarchical clustering.*
5. *Visualization: The results of the clustering are then visualized using techniques such as scatter plots or dendrograms to identify patterns and trends in the data.*
6. *Interpretation: The results of the analysis are then interpreted and communicated to stakeholders, focusing on understanding the relationships between the features and the clusters, and how they relate to the research question or hypothesis.*

It is worth noting (the LLM also mentioned) that this is not a comprehensive list of all possible sequence analysis workflows, but rather a specific one based on the provided context.

Question 7. Where is the data stored?

Here we are asking where authors of a paper published the sequencing data. The LLM was able to provide an answer for only 952 papers. Now we were expecting answers larger than 150 characters that describe the database where the data were stored and answers shorter than 10 characters that contained only the name of a database. Table 9 shows the databases where the data were stored with the total number of publications indicating that.

Table 9: Databases where Sequences are stored according to scientific papers as identified by the LLM

Database name	Number of papers
GenBank	711
BOLD	7
mBRAVE	1
Atlas of Living Australia	1
Mendeley cloud	2
GitHub	3
FigShare	5
UNITE	1

There were 731 publications where the storage database was identified. For 221 papers, the LLM was unable to find the database name in the text. Nevertheless, the most used database for data storage by far is GenBank, the rest of the databases were used as a tool for a specific application of the data.

5. Other Standardisation Observations

A. Sequencing Workflow Related

For INSDC databases, the platforms and instruments are highly standardised within themselves. There is a tightly controlled vocabulary https://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/ena/doc/xsd/sra_1_5/SRA.common.xsd. This is currently more comprehensive than in ontologies such as OBI and the GA4GH experiment metadata group would like to rectify this by populating missing terms to OBI; medium term if wider adoption, this will increase interoperability. This work is part of wider experiment metadata standardisation effort, in which metabarcoding is also included. This also includes sequencing workflows. In D2.3 workflows are more closely investigated.

B. Raw Sequences

The survey initiative databases vary substantially in terms of the raw sequence record counts (Table 38). Somewhat disturbingly over 40% of respondents did not know the magnitude of raw sequence records.

Table 38: The survey databases vary massively in the magnitude of eDNA raw sequence sequence data being incorporated into them.

survey_NReads_Simplified	count
Unknown	27
1M-10M	8
10M-20M	7
100M-500M	6
100K-1M	3
1B	3
<100K	2
40M-50M	1
NotUsable	1
50M-100M	1
20M-30M	1
500M-1B	bc

C. Processed Sequences

Processed sequences were not the main focus of this report, so please see D3.2 for more details. From the survey data there are a multitude of repositories where the data is going to (Table 39). Less than 20% of the survey DBs are reported to submit to INSDC DBs(7), however GBIF(5) and OBIS(5) are also reported. Note that there is participation bias in the survey.

Table 39: Survey ProcessedRepository_Simplified

ProcessedRepository_Simplified	count
Unknown	7
ENA	2
NCBI	5
Figshare	2
Publication_SuppMat	2
Dryad	2
GBIF	5
Zenodo	4
OBIS	5
BioStudies	1
metaPR2	1
Mgnify	1
METU-IMS	1

Figure 18: Survey: most of the processed sequence data is reported being deposited into repositories such as GBIF, OBIS, Zenodo and Dryad

D. Biodiversity Repositories and eDNA

GBIF, OBIS and others have excellent documentation on the eDNA related metadata

<https://docs.gbif-uat.org/publishing-dna-derived-data/en/#data-mapping>

This guide is supported by the [DNA derived data extension for Darwin Core](https://rs.gbif.org/extension/gbif/1.0/dna_derived_data_2021-07-05.xml), which incorporates MlxS terms into the Darwin Core standard

http://rs.gbif.org/extension/gbif/1.0/dna_derived_data_2021-07-05.xml

The OBIS manual contains examples of eDNA datasets formatted following the DwC Core table and DNAderiveddata extension

https://manual.obis.org/dna_data.html#guidelines-for-compiling-genetic-data-edna-and-meta-barcoding-datasets

Figure 19: The [GBIF/ALA/OBIS Figure 3](#) (As below) is a proposed dataflow of eDNA data to data portals such as GBIF and OBIS. This contains many elements of good practice, it is however necessarily hiding much complexity.

Figure 3. Outline of a platform for reporting and publishing DNA sequences and associated metadata (green box) based on existing systems and data standards (grey boxes). An envisioned system for regular (based on machine-to-machine reading of data) update of results (white box) can either read and update the Darwin Core Archive or various administration systems. The data transfer between the various elements (black arrows) will require various degrees of data transformation and harmonization and may include either mechanical or human quality assessment.

E.g. GBIF and OBIS have slight differences in mandatory metadata.

OBIS Metadata

Table 40: OBIS Mandatory Metadata for eDNA Record Submission

Class	Term
Class Occurrence	organismQuantity
Class Occurrence	OrganismQuantityType
Class Occurrence	associatedSequences
Class Event	sampleSizeValue
Class Event	sampleSizeUnit
Class Event	samplingProtocol
Class Identification	identificationRemarks
Class Identification	identificationReferences
Class Identification	verbatimIdentification
Class Taxon	taxonConceptID
Class Material Sample	materialSampleID

(from

https://manual.obis.org/dna_data.html#guidelines-for-compiling-genetic-data-edna-and-metabarcoding-datasets)

The DNADeriveddata extension has no mandatory fields, but also contains several highly recommended metadata fields(all DarwinCore):

- *DNA_sequence*
- *sop*
- *target_gene, target_subfragment*
- *pcr_primer_forward, pcr_primer_reverse, pcr_primer_name_forward, pcr_primer_name_reverse, pcr_primer_reference, pcr_cond*
- *annealingTemp, annealinTempUnit*
- *ampliconSize*

- *env_broad_scale, env_local_scale, env_medium*
- *lib_layout*
- *seq_meth*
- *otu_class_appr, otu_seq_comp_appr, otu_db*

GBIF Mandatory Metadata

(from <https://www.gbif.org/data-quality-requirements-occurrences> and <https://docs.gbif.org/publishing-dna-derived-data/en/>)

For biodiversity data Darwin Core:

Mandatory: *occurrenceID, basisOfRecord, scientificName, eventDate*

Strongly recommended: *countryCode, taxonRank, kingdom, decimalLatitude & decimalLongitude, geodeticDatum, coordinateUncertaintyInMeters, individualCount, organismQuantity & organismQuantityType*

And Dataset Metadata(EML):

Mandatory: *title, description, publishing organization, type, license, contact(s), creator(s), metadata provider(s)*

Strongly Recommended: citation

For the eDNA, GIBF recommends the deposition of the raw sequence to an INSDC archive. With importing the taxonomic annotation of the eDNA to GBIF.

E. eDNA Metadata in Different Repositories

Mitofish Metadata

One cannot submit data to Mitofish, but it takes the eDNA reference data from INSDC DBs. The metadata one can search for: taxonomy, INSDC accession id, voucher specimen numbers and the PubMedId. It allows one to analyse your own eDNA to fish mitochondria markers.

EukBank

The mandatory metadata were at the sample level: ***tax_id, scientific_name, environmental_sample, target_gene, target_subfragment***. These used a specific checklist(ENA UniEuk_Eukbank). At the sequence experimental metadata level: ***instrument_model, library_source, library_selection and library_strategy*** were also needed.

For INSDC Archives the Aquatic samples are Deposited in Different Checklists

For the INSDC submission archives, the sample related data is being submitted to a range of checklists (Table 41 and Table 42). This is important as the checklist chosen determines the mandatory and recommended metadata. The majority of the “aquatic” submissions to the NCBI are being submitted to more appropriate checklists than at the ENA with 77% at the NCBI in the “Metagenome or environmental” checklist and just 11% in a generic checklist . However at the ENA 79% were submitting to the generic checklist, positively 7% were submitted to the “GSC MlxS water” and 1.5% to the “ENA Tara Oceans” checklist (Table 43). Table 42 shows the actual mandatory fields. There are obvious gaps here, with the need to encourage users in using more appropriate aquatic related checklist standards (e.g. ENA),

and possibly the development of aquatic specific packages (e.g. NCBI). It would also be worth investigating the reasons why users prefer certain checklists/packages.

Table 41: NCBI packages and the counts of “aquatic” eDNA raw sequence records

ncbi_reporting_standard	count	percentage
Metagenome or environmental	848179	79.85%
Microbe, viral or environmental	117823	11.09%
Generic	81688	7.69%
Pathogen.env	13739	1.29%
MIGS/MIMS/MIMARKS.food-farm_env;MIMARKS.survey	267	0.03%
MIGS/MIMS/MIMARKS.food-farm_env;MIMARKS.specimen	131	0.01%
MIGS/MIMS/MIMARKS.food-farm_env;MIMS.me	113	0.01%
MIMAG	81	0.01%
pathogen.env	59	0.01%
environmental/food/other;Pathogen	40	0.00%
MIGS.ba;MIGS/MIMS/MIMARKS.host-associated	14	0.00%
MIMS.me;MIGS/MIMS/MIMARKS.wastewater	13	0.00%
Metagenome or environmental;MIMARKS.specimen	13	0.00%
Model organism or animal;Generic	8	0.00%
Viral	4	0.00%
Pathogen.combined.1.0;Pathogen.env	3	0.00%
Invertebrate	2	0.00%
MIGS/MIMS/MIMARKS.food-farm_env;MIGS.eu	2	0.00%
MIGS/MIMS/MIMARKS.food-farm_env;MIGS.ba	1	0.00%
MIMAG.sediment	1	0.00%

Table 42: ENA checklists and the counts of “aquatic” eDNA raw sequence record

ena_checklist_name	count	percentage
ENA default sample checklist	363732	76.42%
GSC MixS water	36896	7.75%
GSC MixS soil	16134	3.39%
GSC MixS sediment	14915	3.13%

ENA UniEuk_EukBank Checklist	10553	2.22%
GSC MlxS plant associated	9006	1.89%
ENA Tara Oceans	7832	1.65%
GSC MlxS miscellaneous natural or artificial environment	7798	1.64%
GSC MlxS wastewater sludge	4410	0.93%
ENA Micro B3	3054	0.64%
GSC MlxS air	624	0.13%
GSC MlxS host associated	396	0.08%
ENA sewage checklist	299	0.06%
ENA Global Microbial Identifier reporting standard checklist GMI_MDM:1.1	254	0.05%
GSC MlxS built environment	78	0.02%

Furthermore when one examines which fields are mandatory in the checklists/packages, large differences can be observed, where there are only two mandatory fields in the ENA default checklist, but sixteen in the more specific “Tara Ocean” checklist (Table 43). Similarly ENA’s GSC water checklist has 125 optional fields and 9 mandatory. For GSC derived checklists the checklists/packages at the NCBI and DDBJ will have similar if not identical numbers of mandatory and optional fields.

Some users use the default checklists as they are trying to do the minimum to get their paper published and sometimes they do not have values for mandatory terms. However, this should not be an issue for users, as there are agreed INSDC values to use where there are missing terms. Fortunately there is a much smaller proportion of generic/default templates used for the aquatic environmental samples at the NCBI. Furthermore, there is a gap in that not enough aquatic related metadata is being captured, as most of it is not mandatory.

Table 43: ENA Counts of the Mandatory(Y), Recommended(R) and optional(N) Fields(Terms) By Checklist

Checklist name	Checklist field mandatory, recommended or not	Mandatory count
ENA Micro B3	N	116
ENA Micro B3	R	2
ENA Micro B3	Y	16
ENA Tara Oceans	N	4
ENA Tara Oceans	R	13
ENA Tara Oceans	Y	16

ENA sewage checklist	N	16
ENA sewage checklist	R	4
ENA sewage checklist	Y	4
ENA default sample checklist	N	28
ENA default sample checklist	Y	2
GSC MlxS agriculture	N	116
GSC MlxS agriculture	R	59
GSC MlxS agriculture	Y	2
GSC MlxS air	N	68
GSC MlxS air	Y	9
GSC MlxS built environment	N	190
GSC MlxS built environment	Y	24
GSC MlxS miscellaneous natural or artificial environment	N	86
GSC MlxS miscellaneous natural or artificial environment	Y	8
GSC MlxS plant associated	N	117
GSC MlxS plant associated	Y	8
GSC MlxS sediment	N	109
GSC MlxS sediment	Y	10
GSC MlxS soil	N	99
GSC MlxS soil	Y	10
GSC MlxS wastewater sludge	N	83
GSC MlxS wastewater sludge	Y	8
GSC MlxS water	N	125
GSC MlxS water	Y	9

Table 44: ENA Checklists with the Mandatory field names

CHECKLIST_NAME	MANDATORY_COUNT	FIELD_NAMES
ENA Micro B3	16	Latitude Start;Longitude Start;Marine Region;Protocol Label;Sampling Campaign;Sampling Platform;Sampling Site;broad-scale environmental context;collection date;depth;environmental medium;environmental package;geographic location (country and/or sea);local environmental context;project name;water temperature
ENA Tara Oceans	16	Latitude Start;Longitude Start;Marine Region;Protocol Label;Salinity Sensor;Sampling Campaign;Sampling Platform;Sampling Station;broad-scale environmental context;collection date;environmental medium;environmental package;geographic location (country and/or sea);local environmental context;project name;water temperature
ENA sewage checklist	4	collection date;geographic location (country and/or sea);investigation type;sewage type
ENA default sample checklist	2	collection date;geographic location (country and/or sea)
GSC MixS agriculture	2	collection date;geographic location (country and/or sea)
GSC MixS air	9	altitude;broad-scale environmental context;collection date;environmental medium;geographic location (country and/or sea);geographic location (latitude);geographic location (longitude);local environmental context;project name
GSC MixS built environment	24	absolute air humidity;air temperature;broad-scale environmental context;building occupancy type;building setting;carbon dioxide;collection date;environmental medium;filter type;geographic location (country and/or sea);geographic location (latitude);geographic location (longitude);heating and cooling system type;indoor space;light type;local environmental context;occupancy at sampling;occupant density at sampling;organism count;project name;relative air humidity;space typical state;typical occupant density;ventilation type
GSC MixS miscellaneous natural or artificial environment	8	broad-scale environmental context;collection date;environmental medium;geographic location (country and/or sea);geographic location (latitude);geographic location (longitude);local environmental context;project name
GSC MixS plant associated	8	broad-scale environmental context;collection date;environmental medium;geographic location (country and/or sea);geographic location (latitude);geographic location (longitude);local environmental context;project name

GSC MixS sediment	10	broad-scale environmental context;collection date;depth;elevation;environmental medium;geographic location (country and/or sea);geographic location (latitude);geographic location (longitude);local environmental context;project name
GSC MixS soil	10	broad-scale environmental context;collection date;depth;elevation;environmental medium;geographic location (country and/or sea);geographic location (latitude);geographic location (longitude);local environmental context;project name
GSC MixS wastewater sludge	8	broad-scale environmental context;collection date;environmental medium;geographic location (country and/or sea);geographic location (latitude);geographic location (longitude);local environmental context;project name
GSC MixS water	9	broad-scale environmental context;collection date;depth;environmental medium;geographic location (country and/or sea);geographic location (latitude);geographic location (longitude);local environmental context;project name

F. Emerging Data and Metadata Standards

The biology standards community over the decades has a long history of improving standards by building on good practice. ISA-Tabs[Sansone 2012] was developed over a decade ago and recently RO-Crates(research objects)[Soiland-Reyes 2020] have been proposed. There are problems with much eDNA relevant metadata not being present in submissions to INSDC databases such as target_genes and scientists using the most minimal checklists[Hassenrück 2021], which illustrated some of the gaps we found.

JSON-schema[link below] is excellent for ensuring metadata standards are being met in individual records. Similarly LinkML[link below] has emerged for specifying metadata standards. Both of the above are compatible as it is easy to transform between each(interoperable).

EML[<https://manual.obis.org/eml.html>] is now being used by both GBIF and OBIS. Due to some of the eDNA repositories not fully using some of those emerging data technologies, metadata gaps will be larger than they ought to be. GBIF and OBIS do seem to be pioneers in using more of these technologies.

Future:

If more time, there are further investigations we would like to have done including:

- A systematic review of eDNA data publishing practices, would have been useful although there is some in the literature [Hassenrück 2021, Jurburg 2020] and to go into more depth in overall FAIRness of eDNA [Berry 2021].
- A similar deep investigation into OBIS/GBIF for eDNA/use of eDNA as that of INSDC would be useful for the sake of comprehensiveness. It was low in the priority list, when we realised that there were no raw eDNA sequences in GBIF and only 40 studies worth in OBIS.

- Investigating the gap between published studies/papers and published datasets. We had thoughts of doing that via the LLM results, but that was too ambitious.

Conclusion

Aquatic eDNA data is distributed amongst many different databases. The two largest archives for aquatic eDNA are probably: 1) The INSDC archives (NCBI, DDBJ, and ENA) containing approximately 1.5 million aquatic raw sequences and 2) Dryad. Much raw sequence data is in INSDC (50-75%), but not all eDNA described in the scientific literature is in INSDC, with about 25% in other archives (e.g. Dryad) and 10-25% missing [Jurburg 2020, Shae 2023]. The larger resources typically archive the eDNA sequence data with INSDC and then do the analysis and taxonomic determination elsewhere e.g. in MGNIFY, OBIS and GBIF.

The gaps identified are listed in Table 1 (Executive summary) and include:

- 1) eDNA raw sequence data is scattered between archives, there is no one place to retrieve all European aquatic eDNA sequence data. However encouragingly 1) For the repositories we examined though, most of the primary raw eDNA sequence data was in INSDC databases. 2) The LLM analysis showed that when scientific literature was mined, the vast majority of environmental sequence (eDNA?) data was stored in an INSDC database. The caveat being that this is when the LLM could identify a storage database which was at best 77% (731/952) of papers, from an original 1,438 papers.
- 2) Anecdotally smaller archives are a) less likely to interconnect with the larger sequence archives and b) often harder to sustain and data can be lost over time.
- 3) Even from INSDC archives, it is difficult to retrieve aquatic European eDNA sequence data, likely due to missing metadata or lack of standardisation.
- 4) The INSDC has no mandated Barcode marker identifier vocabulary. (There is a BARCODE user defined keyword which was originally used to signify COI, but it is not used consistently and not intrinsically for eDNA)
- 5) eDNA raw sequence accession ids seem hard to query or to retrieve from many portals or even their APIs, making federated queries challenging.

Note: Following INSDC spatial temporal mandates in 2023, the country+continent searches will improve. Increasingly, samples have latitude and longitude.

The INSDC raw sequence associated metadata is following minimum standards with GSC MIxS sample checklists, NCBI taxonomy identifiers and INSDC controlled terminology for things like sequence experiment metadata. OBIS and GBIF are using Darwin Core and different taxonomies. Mapping between the GSC MIxS and DwC is improving via a task force [Meyer 2023] and the main taxonomy mappings are in reasonable shape (e.g. WoRMS ↔ NCBI taxonomies). On paper the metadata and data collaboration standards between OBIS and GBIF, seem excellent.

Many of the smaller eDNA archives are using Darwin Core (and several for GSC MIxS) for at least some of their data; however, there is still a gap with those with different standards.

In terms of ecological environments across Europe, there is much diversity of aquatic environments, in marine, freshwater, ground and brackish areas. There are eDNA samples in the major seas surrounding Europe and in many countries. A noticeable gap is that the sampling and archives have been disproportionately lacking from Eastern Europe.

From the taxonomic perspective it is hard to determine, although it appears from the evidence that most “kingdoms” are being sought with different barcode markers. Barcodes are used to identify members to varying degrees of the two superkingdoms: prokaryotes(16S) and eukaryotes abound. For the eukaryotes, barcodes for Fungi (ITS,ITS1), plantae (rbcL, matK, and ITS2) and Animalia (COX1) are abundant in the INSDC archives; 12S the main barcode for fish and amphibians is also common. Yet another gap in INSDC is that the barcodes are not being systematically captured.

References

- Benson DA, Cavanaugh M, Clark K, Karsch-Mizrachi I, Lipman DJ, Ostell J, Sayers EW. GenBank. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2013 Jan;41(Database issue):D36-42. doi: 10.1093/nar/gks1195. Epub 2012 Nov 27. PMID: 23193287; PMCID: PMC3531190.
- Berry et al. 2021. Making environmental DNA (eDNA) biodiversity records globally accessible. *Environmental DNA.* 2021; 3: 699–705. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.173>
- Christiane Hassenrück, Tobias Poprick, Véronique Helfer, Massimiliano Molari, Raissa Meyer, Ivaylo Kostadinov. FAIR enough? A perspective on the status of nucleotide sequence data and metadata on public archives. *bioRxiv* 2021.09.23.461561; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.09.23.461561>
- Field D, Amaral-Zettler L, Cochrane G, Cole JR, Dawyndt P, Garrity GM, et al. (2011) The Genomic Standards Consortium. *PLoS Biol* 9(6): e1001088. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001088>
- GBIF DNA publishing: <https://docs.gbif.org/publishing-dna-derived-data/en/>
- GBIF data quality requirements: <https://www.gbif.org/data-quality-requirements-occurrences>
- GBIF: The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (2024) What is GBIF? Available from <https://www.gbif.org/what-is-gbif> [19 August 2024].
- GSC Mixs standards: <http://www.gensc.org/pages/standards/extensions.html>
- Gaget V, Almuhtaram H, Kibuye F, et al. Benthic cyanobacteria: A utility-centred field study. *Harmful Algae.* 2022 Mar;113:102185. DOI: 10.1016/j.hal.2022.102185. PMID: 35287926.
- INSDC (NCBI, DDBJ, ENA) standards: <https://www.insdc.org/submitting-standards/insdc-controlled-vocabularies/>
- JSON Schema <https://github.com/ison-schema-org>
- Jurburg SD, Konzack M, Eisenhauer N, Heintz-Buschart A. The archives are half-empty: an assessment of the availability of microbial community sequencing data. *Commun Biol.* 2020 Aug 28;3(1):474. doi: 10.1038/s42003-020-01204-9. PMID: 32859925; PMCID: PMC7455719.
- Leigh, D.M., Vandergast, A.G., Hunter, M.E. et al. Best practices for genetic and genomic data archiving. *Nat Ecol Evol* 8, 1224–1232 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-024-02423-7>
- Linked modelling language(LinkML) <https://github.com/linkml>
- Meyer R, Appeltans W, Duncan WD, Dimitrova M, Gan Y-M, Stjernegaard Jeppesen T, Mungall C, Paul DL, Provoost P, Robertson T, Schriml L, Suominen S, Walls R, Sweetlove M, Ung V, Van de Putte A, Wallis E, Wiczorek J, Buttigieg PL (2023) Aligning Standards Communities for Omics Biodiversity Data: Sustainable Darwin Core-MixS Interoperability. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 11: e112420. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.11.e112420>
- OBIS (2024) Ocean Biodiversity Information System. Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO. <https://obis.org>
- Sansone, SA., Rocca-Serra, P., Field, D. et al. Toward interoperable bioscience data. *Nat Genet* 44, 121–126 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.1054>
- Shae et al. 2023. Systematic review of marine environmental DNA metabarcoding studies: toward best practices for data usability and accessibility. *PeerJ* 11:e14993 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.14993>
- Stian Soiland-Reyes, Peter Sefton, Mercè Crosas, Leyla Jael Castro, Frederik Coppens, José M. Fernández, Daniel Garijo, Björn Grüning, Marco La Rosa, Simone Leo, Eoghan Ó Carragáin, Marc Portier, Ana Trisovic, RO-Crate Community, Paul Groth, Carole Goble (2022): Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate. *Data Science* 5(2) <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053>
- Tanizawa Y, Fujisawa T, Kodama Y, Kosuge T, Mashima J, Tanjo T, Nakamura Y. DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ) update report 2022. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2023 Jan 6;51(D1):D101-D105. doi: 10.1093/nar/gkac1083. PMID: 36420889; PMCID: PMC9825463.
- Touvron et al., 2021, Llama 2: Open Foundation and Fine-Tuned Chat Models https://scontent-lhr6-2.xx.fbcdn.net/v/t39.2365-6/10000000_662098952474184_2584067087619170692_n.pdf?_nc_cat=105&ccb=1-7&_nc_sid=3c67a6&_nc_ohc=9f4bqKsK_MMQ7kNvgEvL04M&_nc_ht=scontent-lhr6-2.xx&oh=00_AYBsQ041h5tKPnaeqFMtdlUa3Sz6xHaP4vI2yhLi-Tp98A&oe=66DCE83F
- Tweedie S, Braschi B, Gray KA, Jones TEM, Seal RL, Yates B, Bruford EA. Genenames.org: the HGNC and VGNC resources in 2021. *Nucleic Acids Res.* DOI:10.1093/nar/gkaa980

- Wieczorek J, Bloom D, Guralnick R, Blum S, Döring M, et al. (2012) Darwin Core: An Evolving Community-Developed Biodiversity Data Standard. PLoS ONE 7(1): e29715. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0029715>
- Yuan D, Ahamed A, Burgin J, et al. The European Nucleotide Archive in 2023. Nucleic Acids Research. 2024 Jan;52(D1):D92-D97. DOI: 10.1093/nar/gkad1067. PMID: 37956313; PMCID: PMC10767888.

Data/Code Access

The code used for the analysis is publicly accessible in in GitHub:

<https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/wp2/>

Input Data:

- https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/wp2/blob/main/ena_in/

Generated Data:

- The tables are available as both markdown and tsv: <https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/wp2/tree/main/tables>

The raw data is on a project google drive (access on request):

- deliverable of the required metadata properties: “eDNAqua_M2.1docx”
- A list of eDNA repositories to be reviewed and the raw results can be consulted in the “Joint” tab in a googledocs file called “Databases”
- Questionnaire survey data is in a googledocs file called “eDNA_Survey-Data.xlsx”

Contributions

- Ioannis Kavakiotis and Dawid Krawczyk did the majority of the compilation of the bioinformatics inventory for eDNA (and reference libraries).
- Jorge Moutinho, Pilar Cabezas and Filipe Costa, did the majority of the work with coordinating and collating the questionnaire.
- Dawid Krawczyk and Michal Seweryn performed the LLM and wrote the relevant methodology section. Dawid Krawczyk analysed and wrote up the LLM analysis.
- Most people on the WP2 and WP3 teams provided input into the metadata properties needed to be collected.
- Peter Woollard planned and wrote the draft manuscript, and performed the secondary computational analysis of the inventory and questionnaire.
- Emilie Boulanger, reviewed sections and contributed content for OBIS and GBIF.
- Sofie Derycke, Camila Babo, Eilanne Egge, Joana Pauperio and Filipa Martins, reviewed sections, with very relevant and probing questions and generally provided invaluable quality improving feedback.
- Michal Grabowski and Spiros Papakostas co-led the WP2 and provided much guidance and motivation to all.

Appendix

Searchable Metadata Fields in ENA(INSDC)

The searchable fields in ENA(INSDC) are the ones being explicitly indexed. There is a long tail.

The searchable fields can be found by the following queries for sample(93 fields) and raw sequence records(159 fields). For the raw sequence records many of the metadata fields are inherited from the sample object.

```
curl 'https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/searchFields?dataPortal=ena&result=sample&format=json'  
curl 'https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/searchFields?dataPortal=ena&result=read_run&format=json'
```

All INSDC member archives share a minimal set of metadata standards. The NCBI, ENA and DDBJ have different models of metadata details and ways of storing and indexing the metadata. There will be some metadata easier to query from different INSDC member's portals, so it is worth exploring. Indeed for in D2.3, the NCBI portal was used for that investigation.